

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1905	Paul Ariste	1921	1939	1977		Estonian linguist renowned for his studies of the Finno-Ugric languages (especially Estonian and Votic), Yiddish and Baltic Romani language	1905-1990
1905	Edmond Bordeaux Szekely	1925	1925	1979		Hungarian philologist/linguist, philosopher, psychologist and natural living enthusiast	1905-1979
1905	E. K. Brown	1926		1953		Canadian professor and literary critic	1905-1953
1905	Lionel Trilling	1926		1969		American literary critic, short story writer, essayist, and teacher	1905-1975
1905	Ashley Montagu	1927	1937	1955		British-American anthropologist (race and gender and their relation to politics and development)	1905-1999
1905	Clyde Kluckhohn	1927	1936	1960		American anthropologist and social theorist, best known for his long-term ethnographic work among the Navajo and his contributions to the development of theory of culture within American anthropology	1905-1960
1905	Heinrich E. K. Henel	1927	1927	1973		German-American the Sterling Professor Emeritus of German	1905-1981
1905	Herbert von Einem	1928	1928	1970		German art historian	1905-1983
1905	Anna Granville Hatcher	1928	1934	1976 w		American linguist	1905-1978
1905	Paul Thieme	1928	1928	1971		German Indologist and scholar of Vedic Sanskrit	1905-2001
1905	Hans Jakob Polotsky	1929	1929	1976		Israeli orientalist, linguist, and professor of Semitic languages and Egyptology	1905-1991
1905	Herrlee G. Creel	1929	1929	1974		American Sinologist and philosopher (Chinese philosophy and history)	1905-1994
1905	Isaac Schapera	1929		1969		South African-British social anthropologist	1905-2003
1905	Nikolai Baskakov	1930	1938	1989		Russian Turkologist, linguist, and ethnologist	1905-1996
1905	Eileen Krige	1930	1936	1970 w		South African social anthropologist noted for her research on Zulu and Lovedu cultures	1905-1995
1905	C. W. M. Hart	1930		1969		Austrakian social anthropologist and sociologist	1905-1976
1905	T. B. L. Webster	1930		1967		British English archaeologist and Classicist, known for his studies of Greek comedy	1905-1974
1905	Nechama Leibowitz	1930	1930	1972 w		Latvian-Israeli Orthodox Jewish Bible scholar and commentator	1905-1997
1905	Günther Bornkamm	1930	1930	1971		German New Testament scholar	1905-1990

1905 Fredson Bowers	1931	1934	1975	American bibliographer and scholar of textual editing	1905-1991
1905 Dorothy D. Lee	1931	1931	1963 w	American anthropologist, author and philosopher of cultural anthropology	1905-1975
1905 Irawati Karve	1931	1931	1965 w	Indian anthropologist, sociologist, educationist and writer	1905-1970
1905 Walter Mönch	1931	1931	1972	German Romanist and literary critic	1905-1994
1905 Henri Laoust	1932 No		1976	French Orientalist	1905-1983
1905 Caroline Brady	1933	1935	1953 w	American philologist (Old English and Old Norse works)	1905-1980
1905 Verne F. Ray	1933	1937	1966	American anthropology professor at the University of Washington	1905-2003
1905 Fred McCarthy	1933	1933	1971	Australian anthropologist and archaeologist	1905-1997
1905 Wolfgang Steinitz	1934	1934	1963	German linguist and folklorist	1905-1967
1905 Alfred Bailey	1934	1934	1970	Canadian educator, poet, anthropologist, ethno-historian, and academic administrator	1905-1997
1905 Pahor Labib	1934	1934	1965	Egyptian the world leaders in Egyptology and Coptology	1905-1994
1905 Nora E. Scott	1935 No		1972 w	American Egyptologist and Curator of Egyptian Art at the Metropolitan Museum of Art	1905-1994
1905 Paul Diderichsen	1935	1941	1964	Danish linguist who is known for his model of sentence structure in Danish which has been widely applied to describe the syntax of languages with fixed word order, such as the mainland Scandinavian languages	1905-1964
1905 Михайло Жовтобрюх	1937		1985	Ukrainian linguist	1905-1995
1905 Richard Anthony Parker	1938	1938	1972	American prominent Egyptologist and professor of Egyptology	1905-1993
1905 Robert-Léon Wagner	1939	1939	1982	French Romanist	1905-1982
1905 Cottie Arthur Burland	1948 No		1965	British author and researcher	1905-1983
1905 Arthur John Arberry	1949		1969	British orientalist	1905-1969
1905 Антоніо Fraguas	1953		1975	Spanish important Galicianist historian, ethnographer, and	1905-1999
1905 Byambyn Rinchen	1956	1956	1977	Mongolian literature, a translator of literature and a scholar	1905-1977
1906 George L. Trager	1926	1926	1984	American linguist (phonemics, paralanguage, semantics)	1906-1992

1906	Ezio Franceschini	1928	1928	1969	Italian Latin scholar and philologist, professor of medieval Latin literature	1906-1983
1906	Florence M. Hawley	1928	1934	1971 w	Mexican first anthropologists to work extensively on dendrochronology, or tree-ring dating, archaeological and ethnographic researcher	1906-1991
1906	Alexander Gode	1928	1929	1970	German American linguist, translator and co-creator of the auxiliary language Interlingua	1906-1970
1906	Einar Haugen	1929	1931	1975	Norwegian-American sociolinguist	1906-1994
1906	N. I. Herescu	1929	1929	1961	Romanian classical scholar, essayist, translator and poet	1906-1961
1906	Alice Kober	1929	1932	1950 w	British-American classicist of languages and the decipherment of Linear B (cod)	1906-1950
1906	Voegelin C.F.	1930	1932	1979	American linguist and anthropologist	1906-1986
1906	Meyer Fortes	1930	1930	1975	South African anthropologist (comparative ethnology)	1906-1983
1906	Frederica de Laguna	1930	1933	1975 w	American ethnologist, anthropologist, and archaeologist	1906-2004
1906	Isabel Kelly	1930	1932	1973 w	American anthropologist known for her work with the members of the Coast Miwok tribe, members of the Chemehuevi people in the 1920s and 1930s	1906-1982
1906	Allen Walker Read	1931	1931	1969	American linguist (etymologist and lexicographer), best known for his studies into the words "OK" and "fuck."	1906-2002
1906	Leonard Robert Palmer	No	1931	1971	British classical philologist, Professor of Comparative Philology	1906-1984
1906	Avraham Even-Shoshan	No	1931	1967	Belarusian Hebrew linguist and lexicographer, compiler of the Even-Shoshan dictionary	1906-1984
1906	Adam Falkenstein	No	1931	1966	German Assyriologist	1906-1966
1906	Cleanth Brooks	1931	1931	1975	American literary critic and professor	1906-1994
1906	Michel François	1931	1931	1976	French archivist, palaeographer and historian	1906-1981
1906	Ernst Käsemann	1931	1931	1971	German Lutheran theologian and professor of New Testament	1906-1998
1906	E. Adamson Hoebel	1932	1934	1972	American anthropologist and educator (studies of the legal systems of pre-literate societies)	1906-1993
1906	Emmanuel Kriaras	1932	1938	1986	Greek lexicographer and philologist	1906-2014
1906	Kathleen Mary Tillotson	1932		1971 w	British academic and literary critic, professor of English and distinguished Victorian scholar	1906-2001

1906	Wolfgang Kayser	1932	1932	1960	German Germanist and scholar of literature	1906-1960
1906	Bernhard Bischoff	1933	1933	1974	German historian, paleographer, and philologist	1906-1991
1906	Fred Eggan		1933	1974	American anthropologist best known for his innovative application of the principles of British social anthropology to the study of Native American tribes	1906-1991
		1933				
1906	Frederick S. Hulse	1933	1933	1968	American anthropologist	1906-1990
1906	Wolf Leslau	1934	1938	1973	Polish-American scholar of Semitic languages	1906-2006
1906	Hendrik Brugmans	1934	1934	1972	Dutch politician and academic	1906-1997
1906	Otto Skutsch		1934	1972	German-British classicist and academic, specialising in classical philosophy	1906-1990
		1934				
1906	S. I. Hayakawa		1935	1973	Canadian-American linguist, psychologist, semanticist, teacher, and writer, politician	1906-1992
		1935				
1906	David W. Maurer	1935	1935	1972	American professor of linguistics	1906-1981
1906	Richard Hallock	1935	1935	1971	American Assyriologist and Elamitologist	1906-1980
1906	Lucy Taxis Shoe Meritt		1935	1973 w	American classical archaeologist and a scholar of Greek architectural ornamentation and mouldings	1906-2003
		1935				
1906	Ernest Beaglehole		1940	1965	New Zealand psychologist and ethnologist best known for his work in establishing an anthropological baseline for numerous Pacific Island cultures	1906-1965
		1935				
1906	Rita Lejeune		1935	1977 w	Belgian literary historian who studied the history of the Middle Ages	1906-2009
		1935				
1906	Benedict Wallet Vilakazi		1946	1947	South African Zulu poet, novelist, and educator (the first black South African to receive a Ph.D)	1906-1947
		1936				
1906	Edward Catich			1979	American Roman Catholic priest, teacher, and calligrapher	1906-1979
		1936				
1906	Viktoria Yartseva		1936	1977 w	Russian linguist (in English and Celtic studies and theoretical linguistics)	1906-1999
		1936				
1906	Pent Nurmekund	1937		1986	Estonian linguist, polyglot	1906-1996
1906	Homer Barnett		1939	1974	American anthropologist, thinker, fieldworker, and teacher	1906-1985
		1937				
1906	Margaret Lantis	1939	1939	1974 w	American anthropologist, Eskimologist, and author	1906-2006
1906	Alexander Gode		1939	1970	German-American linguist, translator and the driving force behind the creation of the auxiliary language Interlingua	1906-1970
		1939				

1906 William Cornyn		1944	1971	Canadian-American linguist and author, noted for his expertise in Burmese and Russian language studies, as well as for his research on Athabaskan and Burman etymology	1906-1971
	1943				
1906 Ellen Diggs		1945	1976 w	American Afro anthropologist	1906-1998
1906 Carl-Herman Tillhagen		1960	1972	Swedish folklorist[1] and ethnologist who did extensive research on Scandinavian folklore	1906-2002
	1946				
1906 Pierre Vilar			2003	French historian specialized in the history of Catalonia and hispanism	1906-2003
	1947				
1906 James Verne Dusenberry		1952	1966	American educated and a publicly acclaimed scholar	1906-1966
1907 Ettore Paratore		1927	1982	Italian Latinist and academic	1907-2000
1907 Ignace Gelb		1929	1976	Polish-American ancient historian and Assyriologist (study of writing systems)	1907-1985
	1929				
1907 Alexander Heidel			1955	American Assyriologist and biblical scholar, and a Member of the Research Staff of the Oriental Institute	1907-1955
	1929				
1907 Bernard Bloch		1930	1965	American linguist	1907-1965
1907 Aurelio Macedonio Espinosa Jr.		1932	1972	American professor in Spanish linguistics, focusing on Spanish American folklore	1907-2004
	1930				
1907 Werner Müller		1930	1972	German ethnologist and symbologist	1907-1990
1907 Katharine Bartlett		1930 No	1981 w	American physical anthropologist	1907-2001
1907 Renée Kahane		1931	1973 w	Greek-American Romance philologist and linguist	1907-2002
1907 Helmut Petri		1931	1971	German anthropologist	1907-1986
1907 Kurt Wais		1931	1975	German Romanist, Germanist and comparativist	1907-1995
1907 Gunnar Jarring		1932	1974	Swedish Swedish diplomat and Turkologist	1907-2002
1907 Ze'ev Ben-Haim		1933	1976	Ukrainian-Israeli linguist, former president of the Academy of the Hebrew Language	1907-2013
	1932				
1907 Deborah Lifchitz			1942	Ukrainian-French (Jewish) expert on Semitic languages of Ethiopia	1907-1942
	1932				
1907 Paul H. Kocher		1932	1970	American scholar, author, and professor of English	1907-1998
1907 Julia Averkieva		1932	1980 w	Russian anthropologist and string figure collector	1907-1980
1907 Hans Wolfgang Müller		1932	1967	German Egyptologist	1907-1991
1907 Hans Marchand		1933	1973	German linguist (Romance languages)	1907-1978

1907 Karin Hahn-Hissink	1933	1933	1972 w	German anthropologist whose research on the mythology of peoples living in the eastern lowlands of Bolivia is considered an important contribution to the field	1907-1981
1907 Morris Edward Opler	1933	1933	1977	American anthropologist and advocate of Japanese American civil rights	1907-1996
1907 Froelich Rainey	1933	1935	1977 w	American anthropologist and Director of the University of Pennsylvania Museum of Anthropology and Archaeology	1907-1992
1907 Ludwik Zabrocki	1933	1945	1977	Polish linguist, an expert in German and Indo-European studies	1907-1977
1907 Mircea Eliade	1933	1933	1983	Romanian historian of religion, fiction writer, philosopher, and professor	1907-1986
1907 Samuel Hoyt Elbert	1934	1950	1972	American linguist and folklorist	1907-1997
1907 Dwight Bolinger	1934	1936	1973	American linguist and Professor of Romance Languages and Literatures	1907-1992
1907 Francis Utley	1934	1936	1970	American folklorist, linguist, medievalist, scholar of onomastics and literature, educator, and author	1907-1974
1907 Constantin Regamey	1935	1935	1978	Swiss philologist, orientalist, musician, composer, and critic	1907-1982
1907 Sol Tax	1935	1935	1974	American Afro anthropologist	1907-1995
1907 Greenville Goodwin	No		1940	American anthropologist best known for his participant-observer ethnology work among the Western Apache	1907-1940
1907 John K. Fairbank	1936	1948	1977	American sinologist	1907-1991
1907 Laurence Sickman	1936		1977	American academic, art historian, sinologist and Director of the Nelson-Atkins Museum of Art in Kansas City	1907-1988
1907 Katharine Luomala	1936	1936	1973 w	American anthropologist known for her studies of comparative mythology in Oceania	1907-1992
1907 Wayland Hand	1936	1936	1974	New Zealand-American folklorist	1907-1986
1907 Dennis Fry	1937	1948	1975	British linguist and Professor of Experimental Phonetics	1907-1983
1907 Wilhelm Aarek	1938	1938	1976	Norwegian philologist and educationalist	1907-1999
1907 Ilse Schwidetzky	1938		1975 w	German anthropologist	1907-1997

1907	Mihai Pop		1942	1975	Romanian folklorist, cultural anthropologist and Romanian ethnologist	1907-2000
1907	Mansukhlal Jhaveri	1939		1981	Indian poet, critic, and literary historian of the Gandhian era	1907-1981
1907	Ethel Josephine Alpenfels	1944	1944	1973 w	German-American anthropologist	1907-1981
1907	Baltasar Lopes da Silva	1947		1972	Cape Verdean writer, poet and linguist	1907-1989
1907	Arthur J. O. Anderson	1950		1996	American anthropologist specializing in Aztec culture and	1907-1996
1907	Germaine Tillion	1957		1980 w	French ethnologist, member of the French resistance (Ra	1907-2008
1908	Božo Škerlj	1927	1927	1961	Slovenian anthropologist	1908-1961
1908	Claude Lévi-Strauss		1948	1982	Belgian-French anthropologist and ethnologist, the "further" modern anthropology	1908-2009
1908	Alessandro Lami	1928	1928	1970	Italian literary critic, philologist and essayist	1908-1998
1908	Denys Page	1928	1938	1974	British classical scholar	1908-1978
1908	Cyrus H. Gordon		1930	1989	American scholar of Near Eastern cultures and ancient languages	1908-2001
1908	Rafael Lapesa	1930	1930	1981	Spanish philologist, a historian of language and of Spanish literature	1908-2001
1908	Omer Jodogne	1930	1930	1975	Belgian Romanist and mediaevalist	1908-1996
1908	Elsie Duncan-Jones		1931	1976	British literary scholar, translator, and playwright, and authority on the poet Andrew Marvell	1908-2003
1908	Wolfram von Soden	1931	1931	1976	German Assyriologist of the post-World War II era	1908-1996
1908	Walter Bruno Henning		1931	1967	German scholar of Middle Iranian languages and literature, especially of the corpus discovered by the Turpan expeditions of the early 20th century	1908-1967
1908	Marjorie F. Lambert	1931	No	1969 w	American anthropologist and archaeologist, who primarily studied Native American and Hispanic cultures in the American Southwest	1908-2006
1908	Henry Wassén	1931	No	1973	Swedish social anthropologist and museum head	1908-1996
1908	Godfrey Wilson		1931	1944	British anthropologist who studied social change in Africa	1908-1944
1908	Gonzalo Aguirre Beltrán	1931	1931	1976	Mexican anthropologist known for his studies of marginal populations	1908-1996
1908	André Martinet	1932	1937	1976	French linguist (structural linguistics)	1908-1999
1908	Karl Heinrich Menges	1932	1932	1995	German linguist (Altaic languages)	1908-1999

1908 Raimundo Lida		1943	1979	Argentinean philologist, philosopher of language, literary critic and essayist	1908-1979
	1932				
1908 Emil Staiger		1932	1976	Swiss Professor of German Studies	1908-1987
1908 Eqrem Çabej		1933	1980	Albanian Linguist, Albanologist, Academic	1908-1980
1908 Richard B. Sewall		1933	1976	American professor of English	1908-2003
1908 Kurt Ranke		1933	1973	German ethnologist, Germanist, and folklorist	1908-1985
1908 Jia Lanpo			2001	Chinese palaeoanthropologist, considered a founder of Chinese anthropology	1908-2001
	1933				
1908 George M. McCune		1941	1948	North Korean-American linguist (the McCune–Reischauer romanization of Korean) and Korean historian	1908-1948
	1934				
1908 Else Høst		1941	1968 w	Norwegian literary historian and author	1908-1996
1908 George Shevelov		1949	1977	Ukrainian-American longtime professor of Slavic philology (challenged the prevailing notion of a unified East Slavic language from which Ukrainian, Belarusian and Russian later developed, instead proposing that these languages emerged independently from one another)	1908-2002
	1934				
1908 Niall Ó Dónaill	1934 No		1972	Irish language lexicographer	1908-1995
1908 Leonie Zuntz		1934	1942 w	German Hittitologist	1908-1942
1908 Monica Wilson		1934	1973 w	South African anthropologist, who was professor of social anthropology	1908-1982
	1934				
1908 William W. Howells		1934	1974	American professor of anthropology at Harvard University	1908-2005
	1934				
1908 Otto Kurz			1975	Austrian-British historian and Slade Professor of Fine Art, University of Oxford	1908-1975
	1934				
1908 Victor Lange		1934	1977	German Germanist	1908-1996
1908 Richard William Hunt			1975	British scholar, grammarian, palaeographer, editor, and author of a number of books about medieval history	1908-1979
	1935				
1908 Ruth Landes		1935	1977 w	American cultural anthropologist, pioneer in the study of race and gender relations	1908-1991
	1935				
1908 Brooks Otis		1935	1977	American scholar of Classical languages and literature	1908-1977
1908 George Devereux		1936	1981	Hungarian-French ethnologist and psychoanalyst, often considered the founder of ethnopsychiatry	1908-1985
	1936				

1908 Olof von Feilitzen	1937	1937	1974	Swedish philologist (Old English names)	1908-1976
1908 Boris Vildé			1942	French linguist and ethnographer at the Musée de l'Homme	1908-1942
1908 John Embree	1937	1937	1950	American anthropologist and academic who specialized in the study of Japan	1908-1950
1908 William N. Fenton	1937	1937	1979	American scholar and writer known for his extensive studies of Iroquois history and culture	1908-2005
1908 Stig Wikander	1937	1938	1974	Swedish indologist, iranologist and historian of religions	1908-1983
1908 Peter Charanis	1938		1976	Greek-American scholar of Byzantium and the Voorhees Professor of History at Rutgers University	1908-1985
1908 Malcolm Carr Collier	1939	No	1977	w American anthropologist	1908-1983
1908 Joseph Benjamin Birdsell	1940	1941	1974	American anthropologist who studied Aboriginal Australians	1908-1994
1908 Pedro Laín Entralgo	1940		1978	Spanish physician, historian, author and philosopher (medical history and anthropology)	1908-2001
1908 Neil Ripley Ker	1941	No	1968	British scholar of Anglo-Saxon literature	1908-1982
1908 William A. Lessa	1942	1947	1970	American academic and anthropologist	1908-1997
1908 Albert Lange Fliflet	1944	No	1977	Norwegian philologist and translator	1908-2001
1908 Ted Strehlow			1974	Australian anthropologist who studied the Arrernte (Aranda, Arunta) Aboriginal Australians and their language in Central Australia	1908-1978
1908 Karel Horálek	1944				1908-1978
1908 Eugene Current-Garcia	1945	1945	1978	Czech linguist	1908-1992
		1947	1993	American the Auburn's Hargis Professor Emeritus of American Literature	1908-1995
1908 Paul Imbs	1947		1987	French Romanist, linguist and lexicographer	1908-1987
1908 Donald F. Brown	1948		1976	American archaeologist	1908-2014
1908 Barbara Parker-Mallowan	1949	1949	1993	w British Orientalist noted for his studies of Semitic languages and Assyriology	1908-1993
1908 Dimitrios Loukatos	1949				1908-1993
1908 Dimitrios Loukatos	1950	1950	1985	Greek folklorist-anthropologist and specialist in Greek folk	1908-2003
1909 Guy Sumner Lowman Jr.	1929	1929	1941	American linguist	1909-1941
1909 Doris Zemurray Stone	1929	1930	1973	w American archaeologist and ethnographer, specializing in pre-Columbian Mesoamerica and the so-called "Intermediate Area" of lower Central America	1909-1994
	1930				1909-1994

1909 Morris Swadesh	1931	1933	1967	American linguist (comparative and historical linguistics)	1909--1967
1909 Christoph von Fürer-Haimendorf	1931	1931	1976	Austrian ethnologist (tribal cultures in Northeast India, in the central region, Telangana and in Nepal)	1909-1995
1909 Clellan S. Ford	1931	1931	1972	American anthropologist, co-author of the 1951 book <i>Patterns of Sexual Behavior</i>	1909-1972
1909 Zellig Sabbetai Harris	1932	1934	1979	American structural linguist (discourse analysis, Semitic languages)	1909-1992
1909 Maynard Mack	1932	1936	1978	American literary critic and English professor	1909-2001
1909 Werner Vycichl		1932	1980	Austrian philologist, linguist, and scholar in Berberology, Coptology, and Egyptology, as well as in the areas of Ancient Egyptian, Berber, and Hamito-Semitic (Afroasiatic) comparative linguistics	1909-1999
1909 Eliot Chapple	1933	1933	1969	American anthropologist	1909-2000
1909 Ernst Gombrich	1933	1933	1976	Austrian-British art historian	1909-2001
1909 Dorothy A. Bennett			1969 w	American anthropologist, astronomer, curator, publisher, and author	1909-1999
1909 Hans Wehr	1934	1934	1974	German Arabist	1909-1981
1909 Kenneth H. Jackson			1979	British (Scottish) linguist and a translator who specialised in the Celtic languages	1909-1991
1909 Mashiho Chiri	1935	1954	1961	Japanese (Ainu) linguist and anthropologist, creator of Ainu-Japanese dictionaries	1909-1961
1909 Régine Pernoud	1935	1935	1985 w	French historian and archivist	1909-1998
1909 René Étiemble			1978	French essayist, scholar, novelist, and promoter of Middle Eastern and Asian cultures.	1909-2002
1909 Max Wehrli	1936	1936	1974	Swiss literary scholar and Germanist	1909-1998
1909 G. Ernest Wright		1937	1974	American leading Old Testament scholar and biblical archaeologist	1909-1974
1909 Isabel Aretz	1937	1968	1985 w	Argentinean-Venezuelan researcher, writer, ethnomusicologist and composer	1909-2005
1909 Katherine Dunham		1938	1983 w	American (African) dancer, choreographer, author, educator, anthropologist, and social activist	1909-2006
1909 Alf Hellevik	1938	1938	1977	Norwegian philologist	1909-2001
1909 Douglas Morton Dunlop			1976	British orientalist and scholar of Islamic and Eurasian history	1909-1987
	1938				

1909 Denise Paulme	1940		1975 w	French Africanist and anthropologist	1909-1998
1909 Charles E. Dibble		1942	1978	American academic, anthropologist, linguist, and scholar of pre-Columbian Mesoamerican cultures	1909-2002
1909 María Rosa Alonso	1940				
1909 Tatiana Proskouriakoff	1941	1948	1968 w	Spanish philologist, essayist from the Canary Islands	1909-2011
	No		1977 w	Russian-American Mayanist scholar and archaeologist (deciphering of Maya hieroglyphs, the writing system of the pre-Columbian Maya civilization of Mesoamerica)	1909-1985
1909 Gonzalo Rubio Orbe	1942				
		1954	1994	Ecuadorian anthropologist and historian of the indigenista school	1909-1994
1909 Delmer Brown	1943				
		1946	1977	American academic, historian, author, translator and Japanologist	1909-2011
1909 W. Montgomery Watt	1946				
			1979	British (Scottish) historian, Orientalist, Anglican priest, and academic	1909-2006
1909 Józef Bielawski	1948				
1909 Hugh Edward Blair	1950	1955	1974	Polish Arabist and scholar of Islam	1909-1997
1909 E. Arsenio Manuel	1951	No	1955	American linguist and artist, co-authored the Interlingua C	1909-1967
	1955	1969	2002	Philippine anthropologist, " Father of Philippine Folklore "	1909-2003